

QUIZ**LAST NAME: UWAKWE****FIRST NAME: CALLISTUS****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.
The author used Turabian (footnotes)
The author did use Zotero to insert references
The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Mention the parts that all academic essays, theses, and dissertations must-have.**

- Abstract, Introduction, Hypothesis, Literature Review, Methodology, Argument, Conclusion, and Bibliography.
- Introduction, Thesis Statement, Argument, Tables, and Bibliography.
- Introduction, Body, and Conclusion.¹**
- Title, Problem Statement, Claim, Warrant, Citation, Annexes, and Bibliography.

2. **Why is it important for researchers to include references and citations in their works?**

- To show the researcher's mastery of the topic of research.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019) 1, 3–4.

- To show that other researchers have not done previous research on the researcher's topic.
 - To standardize the research work and make it reader friendly.
 - To avoid a charge of plagiarism and give credit to prior researchers.²**
3. **Which of the following constitute the element(s) of academic research?**
- I The posing of a question worth answering.**
 - II The proffering of an answer supported with good reasons.**
 - III Obtaining supportive data and evidence.**
 - IV Must be original work that contributes to knowledge on the topic.**
- IV.
 - I and IV.
 - I, II, and III.
 - All of the Above.³**
4. **“Your first duty as a researcher is to get the facts right. Your second duty is to tell readers where the facts came from. To that end, you must cite the sources of the facts, ideas, or words that you use in your papers” (Turabian 2013, 86). Mention the type of sources available to a researcher.**
- Facts, ideas, and words.
 - Primary, secondary, and tertiary sources.⁴**
 - Cases, Statutes, and Academic/Professional Journals.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

³ Ibid., 18 – 23.

⁴ Ibid., 24.

- Audio-visual, Books, and Internet Sources.
5. **In the Notes-Bibliography style of citation, when is it better to use endnotes instead of footnotes?**
- When the notes are lengthy and you want to reference tables, and quoted poetry.⁵**
- When you want to make it easier for the reader to follow your references.
- When you want to include substantive comments.
- When you want to state the name of the author, title of work, and details of publication.
6. **“When you do your research, you must record the exact wording, spelling, capitalization, and punctuation of any text you plan to quote...” (Turabian 2013, 201). When is it permissible to modify the terms of a quoted text?**
- I. To fit the syntax of the surrounding text.**
- II. To emphasize important parts of the quotation; to add italics with a caveat.**
- III. To correct minor spelling errors and change the initial letters to either upper or lower case.**
- IV. It is never permissible to modify a quoted text.**
- IV
- I and III.
- I, II, and III.⁶**
- II and III

⁵ Turabian, 95-96.

⁶ Ibid., 210.

7. **What important factors should a researcher consider when choosing a topic for her dissertation:**

I. The potential audience and the intellectual value/worth of the study.

II. The researchers personal, professional goals, and whether the research will be harmful to others.

III. The availability of previous researches on the topic by others.

IV. The potential of the topic to yield voluminous pages of work

IV.

I and III.

I and II.⁷

II and III.

8. **What is the difference between the Turabian and Bluebook's recommendations on when to use block quotes?**

There is no difference between the two recommendations.

The two styles recommend use of block quotes when the text to be quoted is long.

The Turabian style recommends that the writer should use block quotes when the text is five or more lines, while the Bluebook recommends that block quotes be used when the text is more than eighty words.⁸

Turabian recommends that block quotes be used based on the researcher's informed judgment, while the Bluebook advises that you follow the guideline set by the researcher's university or institution.

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap From Beginning to End* (California: SAGE Publications. 2008), 7.

⁸ Turabian, 208; Columbia Law Review et al., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th ed. (Cambridge, Mass: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2010), 27.

9. **As a doctoral candidate writing her dissertation, how many years of existing literature on your topic are you allowed to include in your chapter on literature review?**

- From five years to the current time.
- Between five to ten years predating your study.
- No specific number of years. You should base your decision on personal judgment and the advice of your supervisor.⁹**
- Between ten to twenty years to enable the researcher to provide a holistic historical overview of prior writings on the topic.

10. **Identify the significant role and place of citation software like Zotero and PerfectIt.**

- The researcher should rely solely on the software to insert and edit her citations.
- They play no important role and the researcher is better served inserting his citations manually.
- They are important tools for correctly inserting and editing citations, but the researcher retains responsibility for correctness of her citations.¹⁰**
- Citation software is useful at the early stages of a researcher's career but should be discarded as soon as the researcher becomes experienced in the citation style of his choice.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, 49.

¹⁰ Turabian, 89.

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